

Prototyping Messaging Queue Telemetry Transport in Communication-Based Train Control System to Determine Train Position

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Abstract— Communication-based train control (CBTC) is a railroad automation system and provides effective railroad use because it is different from the traditional signaling concept where CBTC performs reliable communication between trains and stations to provide information on the position of the railroad using moving block concept. CBTC communicated over IEEE 802.11 WLAN network where the connection has a lot of interference from other devices that operated with same frequency 2,4 GHz such as Bluetooth or Mobile devices. It can make the connection unstable. Messaging Queue is the solution to solve this problem. MQTT is an IP-based protocol and has three different reliable message sending QoS Level. In this paper, we provide the difference between QoS Level 0, 1 and 2 for moving block communication using 1:87 or HO scaled miniature train system. The experiment use JavaScript-based simulator application and Wemos as sensor node. The train position is shown in the simulator application worked as expected with QoS Level 1 and QoS Level 2.

Keywords—*cbtc, mqtt, qos, data communication, train control*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of public transportation especially for urban areas is mandatory where the need for time efficiency and integrated mass transportation to provide optimal service to the customers. One of the mass transportation solutions to reduce congestion especially in Indonesia by targeting the construction of 3200 km of railways lines.

Railways in Indonesia still use traditional signalling systems where currently several countries have developed the use of communication-based train control (CBTC). Communication-based train control (CBTC) is an automated train control system using bidirectional train-ground communications to ensure the safe operation of rail vehicles [1]. It can enhance the level of safety and service offered to customers and improve the utilization of railway network infrastructure. CBTC is a modern successor to the traditional railway signaling system using interlockings, track circuits, and signals [2].

IEEE 802.11 based wireless local area network (WLAN) is generally used on CBTC systems although the technology is not developed for use in high mobility environments. WLAN on CBTC generally works at 2.4 GHz frequency. This frequency is also used on other devices such as Bluetooth Devices and Mobile Phones [3]. This can cause interference

which affects data communication between the train and the receiving station.

To resolve the interference that occurs in data communication between trains and stations, we use the Messaging Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol. MQTT can be used for machine to machine communication for existing vehicle networks. MQTT can be used in unstable network conditions and still ensure that the message is received by the recipient [4]. More importantly, it has a Quality of Service feature that guarantees message was received by recipients. Figure 1 shows some QoS features that can be done on the MQTT protocol.

Fig 1. MQTT QoS Level Features

QoS Level 0 sending message only once. Sent message depend on the reliability of network and no effort from publisher to re-transmit the message. QoS Level 1 has a reliable message that ensures at least one message received by the subscriber. If the subscriber does not acknowledge that, the publisher will automatically re-transmit until subscriber acknowledges it, but subscriber sometimes will get duplicated messages. The highest QoS level has a reliable message like QoS Level 1 with exactly one message will receive by subscriber because the publisher waiting for information about sending and received from the subscriber, but it will take a long time to send and received the messages [5].

Our goal is to implement the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) with QoS Level 1 or QoS Level 2 in Communication-based train control (CBTC) over WLAN IP Based Network and evaluate the position of train that displayed in simulator application with miniature train system. In this project, the train system built with miniature train, the application using JavaScript-based application and the sensor node using Wemos microcontroller. The number of messages sent, receive and packet loss will be counted using three different QoS Level to determine the best MQTT QoS Level over unstable network connection over WLAN network.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Prototyping using HO Scale (1:87)

In this study we used prototyping of a simple train system using a miniature train with 1:87 scale or usually called HO scale. We chose prototyping using the HO scale because this prototyping is possible to implement to the real model.

We measure several parameters that we use as testing data, including train speed, moving block sensor data and time obtained from the real time clock sensor that has been installed on the train miniature system. The train miniature that we use has the following specifications: 8 Straight Railroad Block; 4 Wessel Railroad Block and 28 Curved Railways Block. The length of each block is 23cm. Following figure is shown the miniature railroads map.

Fig 1. Railroads Prototype

Result of the HO scale miniature can be see in the following figure below.

Fig 2. HO Scale Miniature

B. MQTT over WLAN Network

Research by Y. Matsumoto et.al [4] shows the use of the MQTT protocol has lower jitter for communication over a WLAN network. Y. Tetsuya inform MQTT has lower round trips with average 100ms when communicating with server / broker [7]. MQTT have a large payload limit because it only uses 2 bytes of header size. Accordingly, MQTT is suitable for use in unstable network environments with large packet size. Based on that, we do experiment to sending data with MQTT protocol over WLAN network using Wemos microcontroller in miniature train system. MQTT is a data-agnostic protocol that can sending data such as binary, text, JSON String or XML format [8]. The data is sending as JSON String format to the Train Control System. We choose JSON String because the Train Control System is a JavaScript-based program which is easier to implement compared to the other format.

Wemos is an ESP8266 based WLAN 802.11 [9]. This device sending position and time data. The data communication process can be seen in the following figure. We use tethering network from mobile phone as Internet Connection for Wemos to simulate unstable network connection.

Fig 3. Data Communication Process

C. Quality of Service Message Queuing

In this research, train miniature sending the data using MQTT with QoS Level 1, because it more effective than QoS 2 [10]. The duplication data can be fixed by adding a real-time clock sensor that synchronizes to NTP Server pool.ntp.org or time.google.com. Figure below shows the flow of sending Moving Block Sensor Data. Every time the train passed the block, Wemos will send the data with maximum 3 times retry limit

Fig 4. Wemos with MQTT QoS 1

Train Control System works to filter the timestamp data. If there are similar sensor position and moving block data, the train control system will check the timestamp data. If the timestamp data exists in the database, the incoming data will be ignored, but if the data does not exist in the database, the Train Control System will insert the data into the database. Filtering is done on the server side by using MongoDB.

Fig 5. Filtering Data in Train Control System

In this research, we use a server and client with specification below:

Table 1. Server Specification

Item	Specification
Operating System	Windows Server 2012 R2 Essentials 64bit
Processor	Intel Xeon CPU E5-2609 v3 @ 1.90 GHz
RAM	16GB
Internet Speed	Download 91.95 Mbps Upload 89.57 Mbps

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Evaluation Data Communication

Experiment is done on a computer with an internet connection download speed of 9.99Mbps and Upload 1.14 Mbps. The simulation using a JavaScript-Based application. That shows the movement of train from moving block sensor data. The application is connected to the MQTT server via WebSocket protocol. The ping statistic of connection to the server can be seen in the following figure below.

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Ping statistics for 167.205.7.226:
    Packets: Sent = 100, Received = 100, Lost = 0 (0% loss),
    Approximate round trip times in milli-seconds:
    Minimum = 14ms, Maximum = 665ms, Average = 64ms
  
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Fig 6. Ping Statistics

We use the testing scenario as follows. Railroad Miniature run clockwise starting from rail block number 1 to rail block number 28. The simulator shows the position of the train on the rail. The first experiment done with QoS Level 0 and the second experiments done with QoS Level 1 and the third experiment done with QoS Level 2. We try deactivating the internet for Wemos every 3 seconds with 1 second delay before activating again to simulate the unstable network connection. Following table is shown the data sent and received for each QoS Level.

Table 2. Moving Block QoS Level 0

Parameters	Experiment		
	1	2	3
Total Data Sent	28	28	28
Total Data Received	25	26	25
Packet Loss	3	2	3
Duplicated Messages	0	0	0

Table 3. Moving Block QoS Level 1

Parameters	Experiment		
	1	2	3
Total Data Sent	28	28	28
Total Data Received	28	30	28
Packet Loss	0	0	0
Duplicated Messages	0	2	0

Table 4. Moving Block QoS Level 2

Parameters	Experiment		
	1	2	3
Total Data Sent	28	28	28
Total Data Received	28	28	28
Packet Loss	0	0	0
Duplicated Messages	0	0	0

In table 2 show the number of packet loss with average 3 packet loss. The number of packets lost affect to moving block indicator in train control system. When the connection is lost, the indicator shows the position in the block number 23. After the connection is reconnected, the train control system only accepts the last data sent from Wemos, so the moving block indicator shows only the movement of the position as shown below. The train control system does not show the moving block movement as expected.

Fig 7. Moving Block QoS Level 0

When using the QoS Level 1 and QoS Level 2, the following figure shown the number of messages published and consumer acknowledge rate. That means the sending message from the Wemos acknowledge by the simulator application.

Fig 8. Publish and Consumer Acknowledge Rate

In the table 3 and table 4 shown no packet loss when using QoS Level 1 and QoS Level 2. The indicator in the simulator application shown movement as expected, but with a delay when the publisher goes offline. The message received at MQTT Broker and waiting for client reconnected again, so MQTT can send the queued message to the client. Following figure shown the indicator in simulator application does not continue the position as in QoS Level 0.

Fig 9. Moving Block QoS Level 1 and 2

When an unstable connection occurs, the train position indicator stops at the block number 20 and the existing data will be stored in the message queue on the server. After the client is reconnected again, messages that have not been received or not acknowledge by the application will be resend to the client, so that the moving block position matches between the data position with the train's real position. Following figure shown the queued messages that ready to resend to the client when the client reconnected again. The number of queued message match with the number of movement indicator shown in figure 9.

Fig 10. Number of Queued Messages

IV. CONCLUSION

This experiment is done to determine the reliability of train position data by using QoS Level 0, 1 and 2 using Wemos as sensor node, HO scaled train miniature system and JavaScript-

based simulator application. Unstable connection simulation is done by deactivating the connection for one second every 3 seconds. QoS Level 0 does not show a good moving block indicator because there are several messages that are not received by the client, QoS Level 1 and Level 2 shows the moving block movement indicator well even though it has some delay because the message is queued in the MQTT Broker. After the client is reconnected with the broker, the message that is queued is sent back by the MQTT broker. The moving block movement in simulator application moved as expected.

V. FUTURE PLANS

In this study only displays moving block positions using reliable message QoS feature from MQTT. This research has not provided a solution for delay problems when the connection is unstable. For further research can try experiment to handle the delay for decision making of train movements.

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